

Invalidating and Destroying All of Mathematics with Cantor's Theorem

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March 25, 2026

Abstract

In this document, by means of Cantor's theorem [1] and the axiom of identity, we invalidate and destroy all of mathematics.

Cantor demonstrates with his theorem [1] that:

$$\forall A \exists B : A < B$$

therefore:

$$\forall \infty \exists \infty : \infty < \infty$$

therefore:

$$\infty < \infty$$

Let us recall the axiom of identity $a = a$; we will assign $a = \infty$.

Proof 1. Now if “ a ” is greater than “ b ”, “ a ” CANNOT be equal to “ b ”. By the axiom of identity. \square

Proof 2. Let us recall that Cantor proved that $\infty < \infty$ (proof 4); reduced to identity this is $a < a$. \square

Proof 3. We had proven that “ $a < a$ ” (proof 1) is invalid, but we have also constructively proven that it is valid (proof 2). \square

Proof 4. Cantor's theorem is valid and accepted. [1] \square

Proof 5. $a \neq a$ because $a < a$ (proof 3). And by the axiom of identity we know that $a = a$, and because $a \neq a$ and $a = a$ are both true, valid, and we proved them constructively, therefore the axiom of identity is invalid. \square

And by the principle of explosion, better known as *ex falso quodlibet*, because the axiom of identity is invalid, the following conclusions are reached:

$$1 \neq 1 \quad \square$$

All of mathematics is broken and invalid. \blacksquare

References

- [1] G. Cantor, *Über eine elementare Frage der Mannigfaltigkeitslehre*, Jahresbericht der Deutschen Mathematiker-Vereinigung, vol. 1, pp. 75–78, 1891.